

ISic4404

I.Sicily inscription 4404

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

greeting

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halicyae

Place of origin (modern)

Salemi

Provenance

Found and excavated on via D'Aguirre in the centre of Salemi, during works to lay a water supply in 1895

Coordinates

37.817374, 12.801307

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 2277

Physical Description

Substantial fragment of a mosaic floor, with wave pattern border surrounding white field, with dolphins in corners, standing figure with cup in centre; a 'doormat' at the lower edge, with greeting inscription above, at entry to room

Dimensions

Height 329 cm

Width 277 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Text set out in large red letters along the lower edge facing the entrant to the room, on a single line

Execution

tessillis

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 170 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. χάρε

Apparatus

Text from photo

Translation

Greetings!

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285013

EDR 114093

PHI 331121

Bibliography

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